

Studies in Sulphur-containing Dyestuffs. Part I. Derivatives of Alkyl and Aryl Sulphido- diphenylmethane.

BY MANGESH V. BETRABET AND GOPAL CHANDRA CHAKRAVARTI.

No direct synthesis of phenylthioxanthenes seems to have been attempted or accomplished. An important method by which phenylthioxanthanols (II) have been prepared is by the action of magnesium phenylbromide upon thioxanthenes (I), (Davis and Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1296 ; Gomberg and Cone, *Annalen*, 1910, 376, 201):—

But even by this method no dyestuff containing auxochromes in the phenyl groups of the thioxanthene residue has been synthesised and therefore these thioxanthenes being colourless are useless in practical dyeing. Another method for the preparation of these compounds, by the action of sulphur sesquioxide upon phenylxanthene and its derivatives, has been described (D.R.P. 65739/1892).

Pope and Howard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 78) devised a very

simple and interesting synthesis of phenylxanthenes by condensing 2:4-dihydroxybenzhydrol with phenol and substituted phenols, and also of phenylacridines and pyronines by condensing the same hydrol with aromatic amines and aminophenols respectively (Pope and Howard, *ibid*, 1910, 97, 972).

We attempted to bring about a similar condensation between the hydrol and aromatic mercaptans with the object of directly synthesising the phenylthioxanthenes by employing a suitable condensing agent. The reaction was expected to proceed as follows:—

When fused zinc chloride was used as the condensing agent, highly insoluble red substances containing zinc in the molecules were invariably obtained, from which the zinc could not be removed by any means. Although these products were found to contain sulphur they were not further investigated on account of the difficulty in their purification and the indefiniteness of their composition. With fused sodium acetate also the desired results could not be obtained. Phosphorus pentoxide could not be used as the 2:4-dihydroxybenzhydrol is insoluble in inert solvents like benzene, xylene, etc. Concentrated sulphuric acid, however, brought about the condensation between aromatic mercaptans and benzhydrol and its derivatives. But the products of the reaction proved to be entirely different from those anticipated. Generally two types of compounds were isolated: (A) *Acidic*, considerably soluble in hot water, alcohol and alkali carbonate solutions: (B) *Neutral*, insoluble in water and most other solvents except pyridine and sometimes alcohol.

The absence of mercaptanic properties in any of these condensation products indicated that the hydrogen of the mercaptanic group enters into the reaction. Moreover, the solubility of A-class of compounds in hot water as well as in alkaline carbonate solutions with the evolution of carbon dioxide suggested the replacement of

a hydrogen atom, preferably the methine one (V), by a sulphonic acid group. The mechanism of the reaction in this condensation appears to be as follows:—

The simultaneous production of the neutral substances (class B) which are always attended with considerable evolution of sulphur dioxide should therefore be represented as below:—

In the above formulæ an assumption has been made that the sulphonic acid is the intermediate product. To verify this the sulphonic acid (VI) was treated with an equivalent quantity of *p*-tolylmercaptan in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid. It was found that this reaction gave 30-40% of the disulphide (VII). This is quite in accordance with the view adopted. Moreover, the mechanism suggested above, would not only render the synthesis of a disulphide containing two different mercaptanic radicle (IX) possible; but also enable the formation of compounds possessing aliphatic (XI) as well as mixed aliphatic and aromatic (XII) radicle. All these expectations have been realised.

The poor yields of the disulphides in all these condensations suggested that we are dealing with a balanced chemical reaction. That this was the case was proved from the fact that when the pure disulphide (VII) was similarly treated with concentrated sulphuric acid, the original sulphonic acid (VI) was regenerated. These two reactions mentioned above further definitely establish the position of the sulphonic acid group in the molecules.

In this paper the condensation products of benzhydrol, 2:4-dihydroxybenzhydrol and 2:4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzhydrol with phenyl mercaptan, *p*-tolylmercaptan, benzyl hydrosulphide and butyl hydrosulphide are described.

The diphenyl-aryl-sulphido-methane sulphonic acids are more coloured than the diphenyl-aryl-disulphido-derivatives. Both of them are red in colour, but dye wool in slightly different shades. The former give a buff-coloured shade while the latter give fawn-coloured shades to wool. A very slight difference in shade is evidenced with a change in the mordant. They dye wool directly but not cotton. The difference in colour between diphenyl-alkyl-sulphido-methane-sulphonic acids and the corresponding disulphide derivatives is very little. Mostly they are deep brown in colour and dye wool in slightly deeper fawn-coloured shade. It has also been observed that unsubstituted diphenyl-aryl-sulphidomethanes are much less coloured. They are faintly brick-red in colour. The potassium salts of these compounds are deep red.

By using freshly prepared zinc chloride having dry hydrochloric acid gas in occlusion, the desired condensation between the

hydroxybenhydrols and substituted phenyl mercaptans has been subsequently realised by us and will form the subject matter for a further communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzhydrol was prepared according to the method described by Marvel and Hansen ("Organic Syntheses," Vol. VIII, 24) and 2:4-dihydroxy- and 2:4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenhydrols were prepared by the method of Pope and Howard (*loc. cit.*).

Condensation of 2:4-Dihydroxybenzhydrol with p-Tolyl Mercaptan.—2:4-Dihydroxybenzhydrol (4 g.) was added in small quantities to a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) and *p*-tolyl-mercaptan (6 g.), and shaken well over a period of two hours. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, then heated on a water-bath for one hour and poured over crushed ice and excess of water. The product was filtered and washed thoroughly with ice-cold water and dried on a porous plate. It was a pasty red mass and presented great difficulties in purification. After repeated extraction with hot benzene and ether, it was obtained in a powdery form. This powder partially dissolved in hot 5% sodium carbonate solution. It was filtered and a residue (A) was obtained. The filtrate was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid solution, cooled in ice and the precipitate filtered and washed thoroughly with cold water. Then it was crystallised from alcohol. *α*-(*p*-Tolylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic acid (VI) was obtained as a dark-red, granular micro-crystalline substance, m.p. 150-159°. (Found: C, 59.3; H, 4.86; S,* 15.6. $C_{20}H_{18}S_2O_5$ requires C, 59.7; H, 4.48; S, 15.9 per cent.).

The *potassium salt* was prepared by adding a saturated solution of potash in absolute alcohol to the sulphonic acid and diluting with water till the whole thing went into solution on warming. Excess of absolute alcohol was then added to precipitate the potassium salt. This was filtered and washed well with absolute alcohol to remove the free potash. It was then dried and obtained as a red crystalline powder. (Found: K, 22.3. $C_{20}H_{15}S_2O_5K_3$ requires K, 22.2 per cent.).

* These compounds are only partially oxidised by nitric acid in the carius' tube. So the estimation of sulphur was carried out by further oxidation of the dried residues from the tubes with fusion mixture.

α : β -(*p*:*p*-Ditolylidimercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethane (VII).—The residue (A) from the previous experiment was soluble only in pyridine, and was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in brick-red, micro-crystalline prisms. Yield about 40%. It decomposes at high temperatures and does not melt up to 300°. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 5.6; S, 14.7. $C_{27}H_{24}S_2O_2$ requires C, 72.9; H, 5.4; S, 14.4 per cent.).

The *potassium salt* was prepared as in the previous experiment. (Found: K, 14.8. $C_{27}H_{22}S_2O_2K_2$ requires K, 15.0 per cent.).

The *silver salt* was prepared from the potassium salt by adding silver nitrate solution till there was complete precipitation. It was warmed, filtered and washed thoroughly with hot water. (Found: Ag, 32.75. $C_{27}H_{22}S_2O_2Ag_2$ requires Ag, 32.85 per cent.).

Condensation of 2:4-Dihydroxybenzhydrol with Phenyl Mercaptan.—2:4-Dihydroxybenzhydrol (4 g.) was added as before to a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) and phenyl mercaptan (3 g.) and the reaction carried out as in the previous experiment. After extraction with benzene and ether, the residue was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and alcohol in red micro-crystalline plates.

α -(*Phenylmercapto*)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic acid (VIII), m.p. 191-195°, dissolves completely in alkali and alkali carbonate solutions. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform and insoluble in inert solvents. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 3.9; S, 15.6. $C_{19}H_{16}S_2O_5$ requires C, 59.76; H, 4.12; S, 15.9 per cent.). In this condensation no disulphido-compound was obtained.

The *potassium salt* was obtained as in the previous cases. (Found: K, 23.3. $C_{19}H_{13}S_2O_5K_3$ requires K, 23.3 per cent.).

Condensation of 2:4-Dihydroxybenzhydrol with Butylhydrosulphide.—The product of the reaction between butyl hydrosulphide (6.6 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) and 2:4-dihydroxybenzhydrol (4.3 g.) was separated as in the case of the tolyl mercaptan derivatives. The residue insoluble in sodium carbonate was crystallised from alcohol in dark-brown prisms. This was the α : β -(*dibutyl*dithio)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethane (XI), m. p. 250° with decomposition. (Found: C, 66.34; H, 8.03; S, 17.3. $C_{21}H_{26}S_2O_2$ requires C, 66.12; H, 7.65; S, 17.02 per cent.).

The *potassium salt* was prepared by the usual method. (Found: K, 16.93. $C_{21}H_{26}S_2O_2K_2$ requires K, 17.25 per cent.). The alkaline filtrate from the dibutyl compound was neutralised

with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a dark-brown precipitate was obtained. *α*-(Butylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic acid (X) was crystallised from alcohol in dark-brown micro-crystalline plates, m. p. 146-147°. (Found: C, 55.1; H, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{20}S_2O_4$ requires C, 55.43; H, 5.4 per cent.).

The potassium salt was obtained as before. (Found: K, 24.51. $C_{17}H_{17}S_2O_5K_3$ requires K, 24.27 per cent.).

Condensation of 2:4-Dihydroxybenzhydrol with Benzyl Mercaptan.

—The condensation was carried out as in the previous experiments. But on pouring into excess of ice-cold water, the solution turned dark brown in colour and no precipitate was deposited even when the solution was cooled in a freezing mixture. So it was treated with powdered calcium carbonate and the mixture was heated and the hot solution filtered. The filtrate, which contained the calcium salt of the sulphonic acid, was treated with sodium carbonate solution till the calcium carbonate was completely precipitated. It was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and then crystallised from a small quantity of water. From this potassium salt the free sulphonic acid was obtained by neutralising with concentrated hydrochloric acid and crystallised from alcohol in brown granular crystals. *α*-(Benzylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic acid has the m.p. 223-225°. Yield 50%. It is completely soluble in alkali carbonate solutions.

The potassium salt prepared as before gave the following result. (Found: K, 22.41. $C_{20}H_{15}S_2O_5K_3$ requires K, 22.24 per cent.).

Action of p-Tolyl Mercaptan upon (p-Tolylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic Acid.

Equimolecular quantities of the mercaptan and the sulphonic acid were condensed in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid as in the previous experiments. The residue from sodium carbonate solution was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in brick-red micro-crystalline prisms, m.p. above 300°. This is identical with the ditolyl disulphido-compound. (VII) originally obtained. Some unchanged sulphonic acid was recovered from the filtrate.

The potassium derivative of the disulphido-compound was prepared as before. (Found: K, 15.1. $C_{27}H_{22}S_2O_2K_2$ requires K, 15.0 per cent.).

Action of Butylhydrosulphide upon α-(Phenylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic Acid.

Equimolecular quantities of the sulphonic acid (1 g.) and the mercaptan were placed in contact with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.), and the experiment was carried out as before. The product which was insoluble in hot sodium carbonate solution was washed well with hot water and crystallised from alcohol in deep brown micro-crystals. Yield 25-30%. (*α*-Phenyl-*β*-butyl-dimercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethane (XII) decomposes above 250°. (Found: C, 69.36; H, 6.51. $C_{23}H_{24}S_2O_2$ requires C, 69.6; H, 6.07 per cent.).

Action of p-Tolyl Mercaptan upon α-(Phenylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic Acid.

The condensation was carried out as in the previous experiments. The product thus obtained was purified by the usual method and isolated in a pure condition by crystallising from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol. Thus *α*-phenyl-*β*-*p*-tolyl-dimercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethane (IX) was obtained in red micro-crystals. Yield 20-30%. The compound decomposes at a high temperature.

Action of concentrated Sulphuric Acid upon αβ-(p: p-Ditolyl-dimercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethane (VII).

αβ-(Di-*p*-tolyl-dimercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethane (1 g.) was treated with 5 gm. of concentrated sulphuric acid and heated on a water-bath for 3 to 4 hours at a temperature of 40 to 60°. The next day it was poured into ice-cold water. Most of the substance went into solution except a small quantity of a red substance. This crude product melted at 148° but on crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 158-159° corresponding to *α*-(*p*-tolylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxydiphenylmethanesulphonic acid. It was completely soluble in hot sodium carbonate solution. The mixed melting point also was 158-159°. The other decomposition products could not be isolated from the filtrate.

Condensation of 2:4-Dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzhydrol with p-Tolyl Mercaptan.—The mercaptan (3.6 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) and 2:4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzhydrol (5.6 g.) were condensed together as before. The product, *α*-(*p*-tolylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxydiphenylmethanesulphonic acid was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and alcohol or alcohol only in red micro-crystalline plates, m.p. 160-161°. It is completely soluble in hot sodium carbonate solution. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, ethyl acetate, etc., insoluble in benzene, toluene etc., while greatly

soluble in acetone, chloroform and pyridine. (Found: C, 58.15; H, 4.80. $C_{21}H_{20}S_2O_6$ requires C, 58.33; H, 4.63 per cent.).

The *potassium* derivative was prepared as before. (Found: K, 21.73. $C_{21}H_{17}O_6S_2K_3$ requires K, 21.43 per cent.).

Condensation of 2:4-Dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzhydrol with Butyl Mercaptan. - 2:4-Dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzhydrol (1 mol.) and butylhydrosulphide ($1\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) were condensed as described in the previous experiment. On crystallisation from alcohol they gave deep brown micro-plates. α -(Butylmercapto)-2:4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxy-diphenylmethanesulphonic acid decomposes at about 265°. It completely dissolves in hot sodium carbonate solution (Found: C, 58.73; H, 6.31. $C_{18}H_{22}S_2O_6$ requires C, 59.02; H, 6.02 per cent.).

The *potassium salt* gave the following result. (Found: K, 22.51. $C_{18}H_{19}S_2O_6K_3$ requires K, 22.85 per cent.).

Condensation of Benzhydrol with Phenyl Mercaptan.—Thiophenol (4 g.) and benzhydrol (4 g.) were condensed as described in the previous experiments. The product was purified by ether and benzene, and finally extracted with a mixture of ethyl acetate and alcohol. The residue was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in colourless micro-prisms, m.p. 221-223°. This is α : β -(diphenyldimercapto)-diphenylmethane. It is insoluble in alkalis. In this case no sulphonic acid derivative could be isolated. (Found: S, 16.52. $C_{25}H_{20}S_2$ requires S, 16.7 per cent.).

Interaction of Benzhydrol with p-Tolyl Mercaptan.—The product of interaction between *p*-tolyl mercaptan (5 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) and benzhydrol (4 g.) was extracted with 25% alcohol, in which a portion dissolved (A). The insoluble residue was then crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in faintly reddish micro-prisms. This is α : β -(*p*-ditolyldimercapto)-diphenylmethane, m.p. 251-252° with previous softening at 250°. (Found: S, 15.25. $C_{26}H_{24}S_2$ requires S, 15.53 per cent.).

α -(*p*-Tolylmercapto)-diphenylmethanesulphonic Acid.—The soluble portion (A) described in the previous experiment was obtained by evaporating off the alcohol and then purified by reprecipitating from the sodium salt by dilute hydrochloric acid solution. It was further purified by crystallisation from alcohol in colourless micro-plates, m.p. 163-164°. The yield was only 15%. (Found: S, 17.1. $C_{20}H_{18}S_2O_3$ requires S, 17.3 per cent.).